

Journal Article

A migrating Indian in Aotearoa: An introduction to Maori culture for newcomers in NZ

Abstract

This article focuses on the author's personal experiences of migration to Aotearoa where she was introduced to Maori culture and its values. It further encapsulates the influences of *Te Ao Maori* in the author's life after migration, especially coming from a country like India with vast similarities to Maori culture in terms of culture, spirituality and colonisation. As the author grows to learn about being a teacher in Aotearoa, this article also sheds light on the values and visions of Maori that guide her practice.

Keywords: Migration, culture, aspiration, colonialism, independence, indigenous, spirituality, *Te Ao Māori*, *Treaty O Waitangi*, multiculturalism, teaching, tikanga.

Introduction

Aotearoa is a land full of vast experiences and people from all over the world making it multicultural in many ways. As I landed at Tamaki Makaurau (Auckland) airport in 2019, my first time in New Zealand, I was exposed to a beautiful culture, with similar values and experiences to my own culture in India. The welcome at the airport with traditional Māori waiata and Haka were my first interactions with Māori culture. From there, I had vast opportunities to learn more and more about the people, places, past and present of Aotearoa and how Māori were the first people, and thus, the most important people on this land. Furthermore, as I studied to become a teacher in Aotearoa, my course began with a traditional welcome at my university called pōwhiri. The ceremony acknowledged the past, the ancestors and those who guide us and led us into praying for our future, new journey and seeking guidance for new knowledge. This experience has really spoken to my heart as I see how the Māori culture focuses on the well-being (*Huaora*) of ourselves and others and understands the importance of spirituality, ancestors and the past. This also spoke to me because of its similarity to my culture and religion, Hinduism in India, as it also preaches connection with ancestors, spirituality and staying grounded. The powhiri was quite similar to the pooja we have in our culture.

These similarities, these influences have shaped who I am today, as a person and as a teacher in Aotearoa.

Who am I? Arriving in New Zealand

People carry with themselves their family values, experiences, visions, past-present-future, funds of knowledge, culture and continue to expand as they gain new experiences and knowledge. "People are competent and have knowledge, and their life experiences have given them that knowledge" (González, Moll, & Amanti, 2006).

Migration is one of the most common factors that change the definition of who you are as a person as you move to new places, learn about the land, people, places and the cultures there

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(Webb, 2015). Moving to Aotearoa has been the major highlight in defining my ideologies, experiences, understanding of people and places and shaping my practice as a teacher for young children.

A fair share of my identity is defined by my introduction to Māori culture and learning how to incorporate these values into my practice. From learning how to live by myself and caring for my well-being, understanding the value of Hauora to learning how to care for young tamariki and supporting the aspirations of families from all cultures and walks of life I have grown a lot as a human. The *Treaty of Waitangi* that I learnt about, is very important to me particularly because of the common factor of colonialism in both New Zealand and India has been a guiding document for me to curb my own stereotypes for different cultures, looking through different lenses and reflecting on myself in daily life. (Education Council, 2017 talks about teachers in Aotearoa acknowledging and incorporating *Treaty Of Waitangi* in their practice).

My migration to New Zealand in some way made me think about the first people migrating to the island of New Zealand and it brings me back to the Māori, their experiences and knowledge that led to me coming onto this land in the present with rich resources. It also reopens the previous wounds that both communities have faced in New Zealand and in India: Colonisation.

Colonisation and its effects: India and Aotearoa.

Many Māori have lost their language, culture, and sense of identity as a result of assimilationist policies and practises over the course of history, which has been detrimental to Māori overall wellbeing (McCarthy 1997, p.30).

The arrival of Europeans in both nations of indigenous people with rich cultures and knowledge has resulted in quite unethical and unfair treatment of people, places and resources. As my introduction to the *Treaty of Waitangi* opened my eyes about the unfair treatment and unjust interpretation that happened with Māori, it also instilled a value of deep relatability. India too had faced similar treatments in the past due to colonisation resulting in loss of land, resources, sovereign society, language, ways of life and overall treatment of people belonging to the region. (Kumar, 2006).

However, India gained complete freedom from the British rule in 1947 with their own language, culture, land, people and places becoming the factors of power. In Aotearoa, we still get to see the continuing effects of colonisation and misinterpretation of *Treaty Of Waitangi* even after acclaimed independence in 1946. (McCarthy, 1997)

How English ways of learning became the predominant language and education system in both India and New Zealand is one after effect that we can still see. In a research by Reese, Keegan, McNaughton, etl 2018, it was observed that “English may already be dominating bilingual children’s Māori language acquisition, as noted by the children's relatively greater proficiency in English than in Māori” (discussions).

Learning about *Tikanga, Te Reo Māori*, past and present of indigenous people in Aotearoa, I am able to recognise the aspirations, visions and goals of Māori for their future generations. From respect to fair treatment, from incorporating tikanga values in schools and institutions to working with whanau to support their children and their success, and unpeeling dominant

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ways of teaching to respect multicultural education in Aotearoa. My experiences in New Zealand and my courses have taught me well. But the question comes up that how do I make a difference in children's lives in Aotearoa? How do I ensure my practices are not some after effect of colonisation? The answers are found as I learn, and they still evolve as I meet more people.

The term Māori for an immigrant teacher: The communities, landmarks, traditions, the cultural representation in New Zealand provides a lot of insightful knowledge on Māori values, cultures, aspirations and effects of European migration to NZ.

One such value that stands out to me is the importance of family. Māori culture values well-being of individuals and believe that whanau well-being contributes towards individual well-being (Ministry Of Education, 2017) Families and communities support each other in growing together and work together to ensure that *Te Reo Māori*, tikanga values, Māori success is achieved. (Ritchie, 2008). This belief is also reflected in the Māori aspirations for young children in Aotearoa especially in schools and early childhood centres. As I learnt about the NZ curriculum and Ministry document, *Te Whaariki* that guides all teachers' practices in NZ, I found that core to all teaching strategies was *Hauora* or well-being of people based on physical, emotional, spiritual and family wellbeing (Ministry Of Education, 2017). Another core aspect of teaching in NZ is the belief that children learn as they interact with the environment - their whanau, their schools, their culture, their religion, the government and the world as it changes (Ministry Of Education, 2017).

Tipuna are the spiritual ancestors and tikanga of Māori. They embody the essence of all living things, including plants, animals and humans. They gave a voice to nature to give life to all things. They are custodians of knowledge passed down from generation to generation. Thus helping the communities sustaining their funds of knowledge and passing these traditions, experiences, languages to their future generations. (Rameka, Soutar, Clayton & Card, 2022).

Among all, connection to ancestors or tipuna, acknowledging the past and spiritual connection with sacred energies, places and people is placed on the topmost tier of Māori culture and values.(Rameka, Soutar, Clayton & Card, 2022).

To sustain life and to make sure that Māori not only survive but thrive, respecting previous knowledge and experiences that guided our ancestors is important. (Nicholls, 2004).

Ancestors are still with us, though not in their physical form. To acknowledge their presence and to connect with them Māori begin and end new journeys and tasks by remembering their tipuna. The past must be remembered as a source of wisdom and knowledge: it will guide us into how to live and govern ourselves, so that we can continue on in this world (Mildon, 2015). I have been privileged enough to experience these powhiri ceremonies, karakia (Māori prayers), waiatas and mihimihi that follow these tikanga practices. As a teacher, these practices have now been part of my routine with children. One can say that connection to cultural practices has helped me remove some of those barriers in my practice that promoted European ways of teaching with multicultural groups of learners.

Young children are lifelong learners and learn through interactions with their environment.

One thing I have learned about learning is that it is continuous, ever changing and dependent on our environment, especially after my experience of migration has proved this. This applied to young children as well. As I have learnt about Māori and their culture, I have also learnt about the Kuapapa Māori model of learning and how children are viewed in this model. *Te Whaariki* is affirmed on its value of children being competent and confident learners, whose learning is continuous and a direct result of interaction with the surroundings (Ministry Of Education, 2017). It encourages all teachers and educators in Aotearoa to encourage independence, appreciate the funds of knowledge children bring and incorporate their cultural knowledge into their learning. NZ curriculum focuses specifically on child well-being and lifelong learning that comes from children's whanau and communities and encourages educators to enhance these values. These align with the values of the kuapapa Māori model of education. The Māori model of education is based on whakapapa (genealogy) and te reo Māori. It is a way of teaching children to think, communicate and function in the world according to their culture, land and beliefs. The model involves learning through traditional Māori ways such as weaving tikanga (traditional protocols), roto takatāpui (using one's own knowledge and strengths), tikanga ngutu/nga-ngutu/tokoī (knowledge of social interactions) and whaikōrero or proverb studies (Ministry Of Education, 2017). The question was, how do I as an immigrant coming from a country that was colonised by Europeans, come to a country that was also colonised by Europeans, unpeel all my stereotypes, all my views on how education should be based on the European education system and become an educator that values children's funds of knowledge and incorporate multicultural practices that encourage cultural learning and whanau aspirations? The answer lies within the children and their whanau, their communities and their experiences. Till now, I have learnt from Māori that

1. Connection with ancestors and past is important and should be acknowledged at all times. The knowledge our ancestors had, helped them survive and build communities and shall be a great part of our learning.
2. It is important to value and understand the tikanga practises our communities follow as they all have meaning. It is also important to pass these on to our moko as cultures thrive, grow and success is ensured when communities are protected, preserved and passed on.
3. Individual growth and success comes from whanau and community well-being, which brings us to the point of valuing our cultural knowledge and learning from it.

Thus, these points have been helping me shape my philosophy of teaching and guiding my pedagogy as a teacher in Aotearoa so far.

Conclusion

In this article, the main focus is an immigrant's journey as an educator in Aotearoa and Māori culture shaping her philosophy and learning. A light has also been shed on the similarities between Māori culture and her own Indian culture especially with a connection of

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colonisation in both the countries and its after effects. The article has also discussed the Kuapapa Māori model of education which the author learnt about in Aotearoa and how her values have been changed once she migrated to the country. Her own experiences with Māori culture and her understanding of *tikanga* Māori values has helped her look at education and learning from different perspectives, cultural and linguistic perspectives and guided her to support Māori children's learning and well-being. In the end, the author has concluded the importance of recognising cultural knowledge, whanau partnerships and funds of knowledge of children, based on the Māori model of learning.

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